

Section Education & Training

RDM Helpdesk Network

Working Group Charter

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1. Motivation

Support is an essential component of an efficient infrastructure for research data management (RDM). Helpdesks¹ guide researchers through this complex landscape and provide reliable support about all questions regarding research data management, including support for technical services, best practices, requirements of funding organizations and legal topics. In NFDI, most consortia have already established or are planning to establish helpdesks to support their specific communities. On a local level, many institutions have set up RDM helpdesks that provide support for the researchers of their own institution. Additional RDM support services are offered by RDM federal state initiatives, by research data centers, by specialist libraries, by the EOSC, and by providers of RDM-relevant tools. Helpdesks cover a wide range of institutions, disciplines, topics, methodologies and target audiences. However, the individual helpdesks are not yet interconnected and therefore cannot complement one another in an efficient way: Given the wide and constantly increasing complexity of RDM, no single helpdesk can provide the expertise for all potential support requests. Therefore, we see great potential in combining the efforts and resources of the existing RDM helpdesks into an efficient and comprehensive national RDM support network in order to provide optimal and tailored RDM support to all researchers and research-related institutions in Germany and in an international context.

2. Objectives

Our main objective is to connect the NFDI consortia helpdesk teams with institutional helpdesks and RDM federal state initiatives so that all users can find and receive optimal support for their RDM needs. This requires the cooperation of RDM helpdesk teams of various institutions and disciplinary backgrounds to exchange experiences and knowledge about RDM infrastructure and workflows, best practices and specific use cases of consulting and documentation.

- Within NFDI, the Working Group will foster structured cooperation of the consortia helpdesks in the case of cross-disciplinary requests that require combined support or different expertise.
- On a national level, the Working Group will coordinate the effort to build, expand and promote a platform to find expertise and contact for specific local or domain-based RDM demands.
- On an international level, the group will identify opportunities for collaboration, most importantly with EOSC.

¹ In this charta the term “Helpdesk” is used in a broad sense and comprises helpdesks as well as any kind of support and consulting services regarding RDM.

3. Work Plan

The Working Group is planning to take the following steps towards the mentioned objectives:

- Establish a community of RDM helpdesk teams from within and outside NFDI. This will build upon the existing mailing list fdm-helpdesks@listserv.dfn.de² and include a regular meeting and workshops. This will allow helpdesk teams to share experiences, potential pitfalls and best practices in establishing and running RDM helpdesks.
- Update and maintain an up-to-date and comprehensive directory of existing RDM helpdesks building on previous efforts, including their respective fields of expertise and target audiences for internal purposes. This will improve the findability and utilization of RDM services and their integration into local RDM structures.
- Establish blueprints for the handling of cross-disciplinary requests that requires expertise from more than one helpdesk, i.e. an organizational, technical, legal and communication model for forwarding support requests between the various helpdesks.
- Agree on basic quality criteria for RDM support processes.
- Create a first point of contact for RDM questions, i.e. a central “signpost” helpdesk that guides customers to the helpdesks appropriate for their request - or a network structure that allows the different helpdesks to redirect the requests to where they are most suitable.
- Provide a contact point for international RDM institutions (i.e. the EOSC helpdesk system) and selected helpdesks in close relationship with the existing NFDI consortia).

Further activities will be specified by the Working Group and may evolve step-by-step. These may include:

- Create a shared knowledge base accessible for all helpdesks that is collaboratively created and updated.
- Identify common topics of RDM that are particularly needed for cross-disciplinary support.
- Develop standards, best practices and apply a quality concept for RDM support processes, including user feedback.
- Establish common documentation standards for support processes.
- Work on a common description model for RDM requirements.
- Contribute to training and qualification curricula and programs for employees of RDM helpdesks.

² <https://www.listserv.dfn.de/sympa/info/fdm-helpdesks> (letzter Zugriff: 04.11.2024).

- Create first-level RDM support that will be available for researchers of institutions that do not (yet) offer generic local RDM support or researchers without institutional affiliation.
- Establish an open discussion forum (like Stack Overflow) for RDM.
- Provide a ticketing system platform that can be used by all helpdesks.
- Develop a concept for a Base4NFDI basic service.

4. Collaboration Plan

We will closely collaborate with all kinds of RDM support initiatives or helpdesk services, including ...

- **RDM federal state initiatives network**³, especially about coordination with RDM helpdesk services offered by the federal states.
- **GO FAIR/GO UNITE! AG FDM-Beschreibungsmodell**⁴ (Working Group RDM Description Model), especially about the formal description model of RDM support processes and about documentation of support cases.⁵
- **EOSC Helpdesk(s)**, especially about connecting RDM helpdesks internationally and the ticketing system Zammad⁶.
- **UAG Schulungen/Fortbildungen of DINI/nestor-AG Forschungsdaten**⁷ (Subgroup Trainings of DINI/nestor Research Data Working Group), on training programmes for helpdesk team members.

In NFDI, we are connected to other NFDI groups and activities:

- **Task Force “User Research”** on identifying and verifying users’ needs.
- **AP1: Target group and needs analysis** of NFDI section Training & Education, most importantly on the RDM competency matrix⁸.

³ https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/FDM-Kontakte#FDM-Landesinitiativen_und_andere_regionale_Netzwerke (letzter Zugriff: 04.11.2024).

⁴ <https://go-unite.de/index.php/ag-fdm-beschreibungsmodell/> (letzter Zugriff: 04.11.2024).

⁵ Helling, P., Lemaire u. a. (2024). Handreichung für die Beratung im Forschungsdatenmanagement. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13684373>.

⁶ <https://zammad.com> (letzter Zugriff: 04.11.2024).

⁷ <https://dini.de/ag/dininestor-ag-forschungsdaten> (letzter Zugriff: 04.11.2024).

⁸ Petersen, B., Engelhardt, C. u a. (2023). Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) für die Zielgruppen Studierende, PhDs und Data Stewards (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8010617>.

- **Working Group “Overall Architecture”** of section Common Infrastructures on the coordination of technical and support services.
- **Base4NFDI** and the basic service teams, especially the basic service RDMTraining4NFDI.
- **AP5: Schulungsformate und Zertifikatskurs** of NFDI section Training & Education, on offering trainings and career paths of employees of RDM helpdesks.

We invite people involved in any RDM support contexts to contribute to this Working Group.

5. Initial Membership List

Name	Institution	NFDI consortia
Judith Engel	MARUM, University of Bremen	NFDI4Biodiversity
Klaus Getzlaff	GEOMAR	NFDI4Earth
Patrick Helling	Data Center for the Humanities (DCH), University of Cologne	NFDI4Memory
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David Linke	LIKAT Rostock	NFDI4Cat
Hela Mehrtens	GEOMAR	NFDI4Earth
Jessica Rex	TU Ilmenau	
Marcus Schmidt	ZALF e. V.	FAIRagro
Thorsten Schwetje	TU Darmstadt	NFDI4Ing
Martha Stellmacher	SLUB Dresden	NFDI4Culture
Justine Vandendorpe	ZB MED	NFDI4Microbiota
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